

Synthesis and characterisation of heterotrinnuclear bis(nitrato)dicopper(II) monozinc(II) complexes derived from some succinoyldihydrazones

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Abstract : The strategy of “complex as ligand” allowed us to synthesize three new heterotrinnuclear complexes of the composition $[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^n)(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ from substituted succinoyldihydrazones in acetonitrile medium [where H_4L^1 = disalicyldehyde succinoyldihydrazone, H_4L^2 = bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)succinoyldihydrazone and H_4L^3 = bis(5-bromosalicyldehyde)succinoyldihydrazone]. The composition of the complexes was established on the basis of elemental analyses, thermoanalytical, molecular weight and mass spectral data. The structure of the complexes has been discussed in the light of data obtained from molar conductance, magnetic moment, electronic, EPR and IR spectral studies. All the metal centres have distorted octahedral stereochemistry in the complexes. The EPR parameters of the complexes indicate that the copper centre has $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital as the ground state. This also reveals the absence of dipole-dipole interaction in the complexes 1 and 3 while presence of weak dipole-dipole interaction in the complex 2 brought about by extended conjugation present in the naphthyl ring. The IR spectral evidences reveal that the dihydrazone is coordinated to the metal centre through phenolate oxygen, enolate oxygen and azomethine nitrogen atoms in enol form. The presence of a band in the region $850\text{--}880\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggests the involvement of enolate oxygen atom in the bridge formation. The nitrate group is bonded to the metal centre as a monodentate ligand. The electron transfer reactions of the complexes have been investigated by cyclic voltammetry.

Keywords : Polynuclear complexes, succinoyldihydrazones, zinc(II), copper(II) complexes, spectroscopic studies, cyclic voltammetric studies.

Introduction

The chemistry of polynuclear transition metal complexes has received a recent surge of interest due to fascinating and versatile properties exhibited by them¹. Current research work concerning the structural and magnetic properties of polynuclear transition-metal compounds is aimed at understanding the structural and chemical features governing electronic exchange coupling through multi-atom bridging ligands². This is because of their occurrence in metalloprotein active sites where the catalytic function depends on coordination between two or more metal centres³. Among multi-atom enzymes, copper occurs in superoxide dismutase in combination with zinc where it catalyses disproportionation of superoxide produced in biological systems from action of enzymes on O_2^- to O_2 and H_2O^4 . Schiff base complexes of transi-

tion metals have been employed to some extent in the development of heterogeneous catalysis, molecular electronics, single-molecule-based magnetism, and photochemistry⁵. Exchange-coupled polynuclear Cu^{II} Schiff base complexes have gained particular attention because of their novel structural and magnetic properties, in addition to being considered as potential biomimic models for a number of key biosystems^{6,7}. Copper chemistry from a magneto-structural point of view is a very extensively studied area, with respect to binuclear systems⁸. However, the synthesis and characterization of trinuclear complexes is only beginning to be appreciated. Further, mono- and polynuclear copper complexes can act as remarkably active and selective catalysts or catalytic precursors for peroxidative oxidation of alkanes under mild conditions⁹.

Salicyldehyde and its derivatives are useful carbonyl

precursors for the synthesis of a large variety of Schiff bases¹⁰. Additional coordinating groups attached to salicylaldehyde increase not only the denticity of the resulted Schiff bases, but also their versatility and ability to generate polynuclear complexes¹¹. The dihydrazones are particular Schiff bases derived from condensation of organic acid hydrazines and *o*-hydroxy aromatic aldehydes and ketones¹²⁻¹⁴. These are special kind of ligands in the sense that they are multidentate possessing as many as eight bonding sites out of which they can utilize utmost six coordinating sites simultaneously in bonding to metal ions in polynuclear complexes. They can offer any set of donor atoms depending upon the preferred stereochemical disposition of the metal valences and the nature of the bonds formed in the coordination process¹⁵. In the present study, we have selected the dihydrazones derived from condensation of succinoyldihydrazines and *o*-hydroxy-aromatic aldehydes and ketones. In succinoyldihydrazones, the two hydrazone parts are joined together through two methylene groups. The succinoyl fraction of the dihydrazones offer greater stability in three dimensional space because of its capability for free rotation about C-C single bond as compared to those in which the two hydrazone groupings are joined together either directly (oxaloyl) or through phenyl or pyridyl groups. The oxaloyl, phenyl or pyridyl fractions by virtue of their planar characteristics impose planarity over the two hydrazone parts reducing its flexibility and reactivity. However, succinoyl dihydrazones by virtue of their greater flexibility are expected to be more reactive ligands than those derived from oxaloyl, phenyl, pyridoyl dihydrazones and to yield more stable complexes. Such dihydrazones, although might exist in only one configuration in free state, in metal complexes can exist in staggered, *anti-cis* or *syn-cis* configuration^{14,16}. There are many factors which might influence the properties of the complexes formed, such as the flexibility or constraints imposed by the chelating ligands, which might favour a geometry preferred by one metal ion oxidation state but not the others, the types of donor atoms (i.e. O vs N vs S); the geometry of the coordinated complexes, the electronegativity of the groups, the bulky nature of the atoms present in the ligands, the denticity of the ligands, preferred stereochemical disposition of the metal valences and the nature of the bonds formed in the coordination processes. The dihydrazones

in the present study contain salicyldimine, 5-bromo-salicyldimine and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldimine in their molecular skeleton. Further, as we go from salicyldimine dihydrazone to naphthaldimine dihydrazone to 5-bromosalicylalimine dihydrazone, the bulkyness and electronegativity both increase in the same order. Among the methodologies that are used for the construction of polynuclear assemblies of predesigned compositions, the most popular method is stepwise construction of mononuclear transition metal complexes of multidentate ligands in which some of the donor sites are unoccupied, which often serve as efficient building blocks¹⁷. Although some such compounds have been prepared by using either well-designed organic ligands or transition metal complex ligands¹⁸ yet much remains to be learnt.

A survey of literature reveals that although some isolated studies are available on metal complexes of succinoyldihydrazones and related hydrazones^{19,20}, yet the systematic study on the synthesis and characterization of heterometal complexes of succinoylhydrazones is absent in spite of their highly flexible nature. Moreover, the synthesis and characterization of trinuclear complexes with intervening two methylene functions in multidentate ligands is almost non-existent¹² to the best of our knowledge.

Keeping the above importance of copper in heterometal enzymes, catalysis and magnetochemistry in mind and meagre amount of research work^{21,22} on hetero trinuclear transition metal complexes and the absence of work on trinuclear metal complexes of succinoylhydrazones, the present paper reports the results of our investigation on the synthesis and structural elucidation of heterotrinuclear Zn-Cu complexes of some succinoyldihydrazones (Fig. 1).

Results and discussion

Synthesis of the heterometallic complexes were achieved by reaction of precursor zinc(II) complexes $[Zn(H_2L^n)(H_2O)_2]$ with copper(II) nitrate in acetonitrile under reflux taking precursor complex : $Cu(NO_3)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ molar ratio at 1 : 3. Green solutions were formed rapidly, which precipitated compounds on cooling. The compounds were characterized by elemental analysis, spectroscopic and electrochemical analysis. On the basis of various analytical and mass spectral data, the complexes

Fig. 1.

R_1 R_2 X Dihydrazone ligand

H H H Disalicylaldehydesuccinoyldihydrazone (H_4L^1)

H 5,6-benzo H Bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)succinoyldihydrazone (H_4L^2)

H H Br Bis(5-bromosalicylaldehyde)succinoyldihydrazone (H_4L^3)

have been suggested to have the stoichiometry $[ZnCu_2(L^n)(NO_3)_2(H_2O)_8].2H_2O$ ($L^n = H_4L^1, H_4L^2$ and H_4L^3). All of the complexes are insoluble in water and common organic solvents but are soluble in highly coordinating solvents such as DMSO and DMF. All of the complexes show weight loss corresponding to two water molecules at 110 °C, while eight water molecules at 180 °C when heated in an electronic oven for 4 h at each of the temperature. The weight loss corresponding to two water molecules at 110 °C suggests that these water molecules are present in the lattice structure of the complexes. The eight water molecules lost at 180 °C suggest that they are present in the first coordination sphere around metal centre.

The vapours evolved at 110 °C and 180 °C in the complexes were passed through a trap containing copper sulphate which turned blue. This confirmed that the vapours in the complexes originated from water molecules. The complexes in general decompose above 300 °C. High decomposition temperature of the complexes indicates their comparatively higher ionic character.

An effort was taken up to crystallize the complexes in various solvent systems under different experimental conditions. Both saturated and dilute solutions of the complexes in various solvent systems such as DMSO, DMF, DMSO- CH_3CN , DMF- CH_3CN , DMSO- CH_2Cl_2 , DMF- CH_2Cl_2 each was kept for 1 and 2 months under observa-

tion at ambient temperature to grow crystals. Further, the solutions were gently evaporated at 40 °C, 50 °C and 60 °C in a hot air electronic oven to promote crystal growth. Moreover, an effort was made to grow crystal from the reaction mixture by layering a solution of the metal salts with a solution containing the ligand in methanol solutions. Again, the metal salt solutions mixed with the ligand solutions in DMSO and DMF were also layered with diethyl ether and resulting solution in a small beaker was kept in a bigger beaker containing n-hexane. Further, the monometallic precursor complex (0.115 mmol) and $Cu(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (0.345 mmol) were placed in the main arm of a branched tube (branch tube method). A mixture of ACN and DMSO (15 : 85 v/v, 15 mL) was carefully added to fill the arms, the tube was sealed and reagents containing arm immersed in an oil bath at 60 °C, while the other arm was kept at ambient temperature. Unfortunately, in all our efforts, only amorphous compounds precipitated which prevented analysis of the complexes by X-ray crystallization. When similar effort was attempted for the ligands, H_4L^2 could be crystallized out from DMSO solution and crystal structure could be determined by X-ray crystallography.

Mass spectral studies :

All of the complexes have been characterized by mass spectroscopy. The mass spectrum of the complex **2** is shown in Fig. 2. The complexes **1** to **3** show a molecular ion peak at m/z value of 760.67, 1069.59 and 988.52, respectively. The m/z value for these peaks is close to the mass of the molecular ions $[ZnCu_2(L^1)(NO_3)(DMSO)_2]^+$ (760.49), $[ZnCu_2(L^2)(NO_3)(DMSO)_4(H_2O)_3]^+$ (1070.49) and $[ZnCu_2(L^3)(NO_3)(DMSO)_2(H_2O)_4]^+$ (988.49), respectively. Hence, these peaks owe their origin to these molecular ions. The molecular ion $[ZnCu_2(L^1)(NO_3)(DMSO)_2]^+$ for the complex **1** arises, most probably, from the loss of one nitrato group and all water molecules from the coordination sphere of the complex followed by coordination of two DMSO molecules from the solvent. Similarly, the molecular ion $[ZnCu_2(L^2)(NO_3)(DMSO)_4(H_2O)_3]^+$ arises from the loss of one nitrato group and five water molecules from the coordination sphere of the complex **2** followed by coordination of four DMSO molecules while in complex **3**, the molecular ion $[ZnCu_2(L^3)(NO_3)(DMSO)_2(H_2O)_4]^+$ (988.49), arises from

Fig. 2. Mass spectrum of the complex $[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^2)(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2) in DMSO solution.

loss of one nitrate group and four water molecules from coordination sphere followed by coordination of two DMSO molecules. The complex 3 shows another peak at

m/z value of 736.46. This m/z value is close to the mass of the molecular ion $[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^3)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ (736.49). Hence, it is assigned to the molecular ion

$[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^3)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ (736.46) which results from the loss of two nitrato and six water molecules from the coordination sphere of the complex.

The existence of molecular ions $[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^1)(\text{NO}_3)(\text{DMSO})_2]^+$ (760.49), $[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^2)\text{NO}_3(\text{DMSO})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]^+$ (1070.49) and $[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^3)(\text{NO}_3)(\text{DMSO})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^+$ (990.49), $[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^3)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ (736.49) in the mass spectra of the complexes suggests that all of them are monomeric in nature.

Molecular weight :

The molecular weight of the complexes has been determined in DMSO solution by freezing point depression method due to insolubility of the complexes in non-coordinating solvents. The experimental values of the molecular weights for the complexes are (1020 ± 50) , (1180 ± 55) and (1230 ± 60) respectively, which are very close to the theoretical value for the monomer formulation and much less than the theoretical values for the dimer formulation. This suggests that the complexes are monomeric in nature. However, the experimental value of the molecular weight is considerably higher than the theoretical value calculated on the basis of the monomer formulation. This may be related to replacement of H_2O molecules from the complexes by DMSO molecules in the solution.

Molar conductance :

The molar conductance values for the complexes in DMSO solution at 10^{-3} M dilution are in the range $1.2\text{--}1.7 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$. These values are consistent with their non-electrolytic nature in this medium²⁵.

Magnetic moment :

The μ_{eff} value for the complexes are 2.28, 2.35 and 2.50 BM per molecular formula while per copper unit are 1.61, 1.66 and 1.77 BM, respectively. The μ_{eff} values for the complexes **1** and **2** per molecular and per

formula weight are slightly less than the value of 2.44 BM for dinuclear copper(II) complexes and 1.73 BM per mononuclear copper(II) complexes involving no metal-metal interaction. These μ_{eff} values suggest very weak interaction between copper centres in the structural unit of the complexes. Such extremely weak M-M interaction might result from poor electron exchange between copper centres due to superexchange mechanism involving ligand bridging itself and enolate oxygen bridging via filled d^{10} orbitals of the intervening zinc(II) atom²⁶. The μ_{eff} value suggests the absence of anion bridging in these complexes and is corroborated from the fact that nitrato group is monodentate in the complexes. On the other hand, the μ_{eff} value of 2.50 BM for complex **3** per molecular formula and 1.77 BM per mononuclear copper centre rules out the possibility of the presence of any copper-copper interaction in the structural unit of the complex. A minute examination of the magnitude of μ_{eff} value for the complexes reveals a regular increase in going from salicylaldimine dihydrazone to 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalaldimine dihydrazone to 5-bromo-salicylaldimine dihydrazone. Such a regular variation in the effective magnetic moment value of the complexes in going from salicylaldimine dihydrazone to 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalaldimine dihydrazone to 5-bromosalicylaldimine dihydrazone complexes may be rationalized in terms of increasing steric crowding in the complexes. As we move from salicylaldimine dihydrazone to 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalaldimine dihydrazone to 5-bromosalicylaldimine dihydrazone ligand, the size of the ligands increases in the same order. As a result, the steric crowding in the coordinated ligand increases which, in turn, increases the distance between the metal centres. This difference in the magnetic behaviour of the complex **3** as compared to those of the complexes **1** and **2** might be attributed to bulky nature of bromide atom present on the salicylaldiminato part of the ligands. Because of the

Table 1. Peak assignment in the mass spectra of heterotrinnuclear zinc(II) and copper(II) complexes

Sl. No.	Complex	Molecular ions	Expt. mass (m/z)	Theo. mass
1.	$[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^1)(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^1)(\text{NO}_3)(\text{DMSO})_2]^+$	760.67	760.49
2.	$[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^2)(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^2)(\text{NO}_3)(\text{DMSO})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]^+$	1070.59	1070.49
3.	$[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^3)(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^3)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ $[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^3)(\text{NO}_3)(\text{DMSO})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^+$	736.46 988.52	736.49 988.49

bulky nature of bromine atom, the copper centres are so much so separated from one another that they do not interact with one another at all.

Electron paramagnetic resonance :

The X-band EPR spectra for the complexes have been recorded at RT and LNT in powder as well as DMSO glass at LNT. The various EPR parameters for the complexes have been set out in Table 2. The EPR spectra for the complexes have been given in Figs. 3–5. The present ligand can react with the metal ions in metal complexes either in staggered configuration or *syn-cis* or *anti-cis* configuration^{24,27}. The bonding of the ligand to the metal centre in the staggered configuration in the present complexes is impossible, because it would, at the most, give rise to binuclear complexes only with the bivalent metal ions. If a trinuclear complex is to be formed, the only option available to the ligand is to exist in the *cis*-configuration and react with the metal ions^{24,27}. Thus, the stereochemical consideration of the ligand suggests that its reaction with the metal ions in *cis*-configuration would give rise to trinuclear complexes.

The EPR spectra for the complexes at LNT look like an isolated axial copper(II) ion in solid as well solution state. The EPR spectra of the complexes **2** and **3** are isotropic at RT in solid state with g_{av} value equal to 2.158 and 2.039 while that of the complex **1** is anisotropic with $g_{||}$ and g_{\perp} values equal to 2.208 and 2.051. The complex shows copper hyperfine splitting in $g_{||}$ and g_{\perp} region both (Table 2). The average hyperfine splitting constants observed are 150 G and 20 G, respectively. However, at LNT in the solid state as well as solution state, the copper hyperfine splitting are observed in all of the complexes in $g_{||}$ region only. The average hyperfine coupling constant for the complexes at LNT in the solid state is in the region 120–150 G which is the value found for monomeric copper complexes. These values suggests the possibility of very weak metal-metal interaction in the structural unit of the complexes. In view of the splitting of line in the $g_{||}$ and g_{\perp} region in case of complexes, the intermolecular magnetic effect can be considered to be very small or insignificant. This is also supported by room temperature magnetic moment value in the region 2.28–2.50 per molecular formula and 1.59–1.77 BM per copper(II) ion for the complexes which suggests the pres-

Table 2. Magnetic parameters and electronic spectral data for heterotrinnuclear Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes derived from succinoyldihydrazones

Sl. No.	Complex	Magnetic moment		Temp.	Solid/ Solution	$g_{ }$	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	$A_{ }$ (A_3)	A_{\perp} (A_1)	A_{av}	$g_{ }/A_{ }$	Electronic spectral bands		
		Per molecular formula	Per emperial formula										Solid	Solution	
1.	[ZnCu ₂ (L ¹)(NO ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₈].2H ₂ O	2.28	1.61	RT	Powder	2.208	2.051	2.103	150	20	63.3	157.9	305 (17050), 320 (16030),		
				LNT	Powder	2.208	2.051	2.103	150	-	-	157.9	673	380 (12546), 665 (20)	
				LNT	Solution	2.197	2.071	2.113	120	-	-	150.3	-	[293 (7100), 330 (520)] ^a	
2.	[ZnCu ₂ (L ²)(NO ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₈].2H ₂ O	2.35	1.66	RT	Powder	-	-	2.158	-	-	-	-	332 (23000), 418 (27000),		
				LNT	Powder	2.223	2.064	2.117	150	-	-	159.0	700	690 (25)	
				LNT	Solution	2.125	2.064	2.084	60	-	-	-	-	[312 (5400), 327 (6200),	
3.	[ZnCu ₂ (L ³)(NO ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₈].2H ₂ O	2.50	1.77	RT	Powder	2.227	2.077	2.039	120	-	-	199.1	365 (5800), 382 (5400)] ^a		
				LNT	Powder	2.200	2.064	2.109	130	-	-	181.5	662	292 (17000), 332 (30000),	
				LNT	Solution	2.197	2.071	2.113	120	-	-	181.3	-	410 (40000), 700 (163)	
														[292 (8500), 340 (6600),	
															352 (5600)]

^aLigand bands are given in square bracket.

ence of very weak antiferromagnetic intramolecular coupling. Also because, a seven-line spectral feature was not observed for the complexes **1** and **3** at LNT, dipole-dipole interaction seems likely to be the source of exchange.

At 77 K, dimethyl sulphoxide glass spectrum was obtained for the complexes which are shown in Figs. 3–5. The g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values for the complexes are in the region 2.125–2.197 and 2.064–2.071, respectively, while hyperfine coupling constant A_{\parallel} is in the region 120 G for the complexes **1** and **3** and 60 G for the complex **2**. The parameters obtained are typical of a tetragonally distorted octahedral environment around the copper(II) centre with $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} \sim 2$. Three of the expected four hyperfine signals are seen with the fourth one hidden under g_{\perp} lines. No additional hyperfine lines are seen in the spectrum of frozen DMSO solution at LNT which rules out the possibility of existence of either different copper environment within the complexes, perhaps involving partial salvation or of the existence of even weak dipole-dipole coupling between the copper centres. The possibility of occurrence of different copper environments within the complex is also ruled out on the basis of UV-Vis solution studies which show that the principal

dihydrazone ligand remains coordinated to the metal centre in DMSO solution. This consideration points to the absence of weak dipole-dipole coupling between the copper centre in the complexes **1** and **3**. This observation is similar to those of Brudenell *et al.*²⁸ who reported that the increasing Cu...Cu separation brought about by the increasing length of the bridge between the two copper centres decreases the dipole-dipole coupling. The same explanation may be advanced in the present case where Cu...Cu separation have been increased by intervening zinc atom and the bulky naphthyl fragment and bromo substituent on the phenyl ring in complexes **2** and **3**, respectively. This phenomenon has also been documented in other studies of copper complexes²⁹. However, weak half-field line ($\Delta M_s = \pm 2$) is not observable at 1500 G suggesting that the dipole-dipole coupling operating between two copper centres is either absent or very weak.

Although the complexes **1** and **3** show, in general four lines in the g_{\parallel} region in the DMSO glass spectra, the fourth line weakly appearing because of its overlapping with the strong line in the g_{\perp} region. However, the amplified spectrum of the complex **2** on close examination shows six weakly resolved peaks for the low field side of the perpendicular region. The dissociation of the com-

Fig. 3. EPR spectrum of the complex $[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^1)(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**) in DMSO glass at LNT ($f = 9.1 \text{ Mz}$).

plex is unlikely to be responsible for hyperfine lines since the electronic spectra of the complexes suggests the principal dihydrazone ligand is coordinated to the metal centre in the DMSO solution. This shows considerable weak coupling between copper-copper centres in the complex. Such a difference in the LNT spectrum of the complex **2**

in DMSO solution as compared to those of the complexes **1** and **3** may safely be attributed to the presence of extended conjugation in the naphthyl ring as compared to those in the phenyl rings in the complexes **1** and **3**. Another factor which might contribute partially to copper-copper coupling in complex **2**, is the flexibility in the

Fig. 4. EPR spectrum of the complex $[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^2)(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**2**) in DMSO glass at LNT ($f = 9.1 \text{ Mz}$).

Fig. 5. EPR spectrum of the complex $[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^3)(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**3**) in DMSO glass at LNT ($f = 9.1 \text{ Mz}$).

coordinated ligand backbone in DMSO solution. Due to this the copper centres might come closer to each other interacting with one another. In complex **3**, the two copper centres might not come sufficiently close due of bulky nature of the bromide substituent on phenyl ring. A careful minute examination of the LNT spectrum further reveals the weak splitting of the signals in the g_{\parallel} region. In the simple, 14 lines that is two sets (due to zero field splitting) of seven copper hyperfine lines would be expected³⁰ in the parallel signal for such copper complexes. It is quite reasonable to assume that the two sets of seven lines overlap leading to the appearance of fewer than 14 lines. In the parallel signal of this DMSO glass spectrum, ten peaks can be tentatively identified, although very weak, as indicated in Fig. 4. The highest field peaks of the high field, two sets of seven peaks is not readily visible due to low intensity/or overlapping with the perpendicular signal. It is important to note that this assignment gives $A_{\parallel} = 60$ G, which is close to the value i.e. half of the monomer value for other binuclear copper complexes **1** and **3**, with magnetic exchange.

The extent of this coupling depends on the Cu...Cu separation, which is a function of the size of the bonded groups and conjugation present in the ligand. Thus EPR spectroscopy suggests that dipole-dipole coupling exists in the 2-hydroxy-naphthaldiminato complex but not in the salicylaldiminato and 5-bromosalicylaldiminato complexes. The behaviour of the extremely weakly exchange coupled systems is well documented²⁹. In such systems, the presence of, for example, magnetic dipolar interaction with strengths in fractions of a wave number, can give rise to spectra that are very different from those of the uncoupled systems³¹. Such behaviour has been observed by Murase *et al.* for the binuclear Cu^{II} complexes of a series of alkyl-bridged unsaturated bis(tetradentate)-macrocycles³². The room temperature magnetic moments, for the complex **2** was slightly less than the spin-only for two unpaired electrons without any M-M interaction. The tendency of A_{\parallel} to decrease with an increase of g_{\parallel} is an index of an increase in tetrahedral distortion in the square planar geometry in the coordination sphere of copper. However, in the case of octahedral or square pyramidal complexes, this has been related to the increased distortion in the equatorial plane. In order to quantify the degree of distortion in the copper(II) complexes, we have

selected the factor $g_{\parallel}/A_{\parallel}$ obtained from EPR spectra which is considered as an empirical index of distortion in the equatorial plane³³. It ranges between 105 and 135 for square planar equatorial configuration depending upon the nature of the coordinated atom, highly distorted structure in the equatorial plane can have larger values³³. The $g_{\parallel}/A_{\parallel}$ quotients for complex **1** are 157.9 and 150.3 in solid and DMSO solution at LNT, respectively, while for the complex **3**, they are high and lie in the range 181.5–195.7. The $g_{\parallel}/A_{\parallel}$ value for the complexes fall in the region 150.3–195.7 which are much deviated from the range reported for square planar equatorial configuration suggesting that in the complexes there is appreciable distortion in the equatorial plane from planarity³⁴. This clearly reflects a lower symmetry for the complexes³⁴.

Electronic spectroscopy :

The UV-Visible spectra of the complexes have been recorded in the solid state and DMSO solution both (Table 2). The disalicylaldehyde succinoyl dihydrazone shows bands at 293 nm and 330 nm, while the remaining two dihydrazones show four and three bands respectively in the region 292–382 nm. The bands around 300 and 330 nm are assigned to the intra-ligand $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition while the bands around 360 and 380 nm in case of ligands H_4L^2 and H_4L^3 are assigned to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition³⁵.

The solid state spectra of complexes display a broad band centred in the region 660–700 nm. This band is attributed to $d-d$ transitions. The $d-d$ transition occurs at around 800 nm in the octahedral complexes and around 1200 nm in tetrahedral complexes³⁶. The position of the $d-d$ band shifts to lower wavelength as the distortion in the complexes increases. The position of the $d-d$ band and its shape and molar extinction coefficient suggests that the copper centre has distorted octahedral geometry in complexes.

The complexes display three to four well resolved peaks in the region 300–1100 nm in DMSO solution. The ligand band in the region 292–327 nm in the uncoordinated ligand shifts by 5–30 nm to longer wavelength and appears in the region 305–332 nm. This band splits into two bands in the complex **1**. The ligand band in the region 352–382 nm shows considerable red shift by about 50–60 nm on complexation and appears in the region 394–418 nm. Such a feature associated with the red shift

of the ligand bands provides a good evidence for the chelation of dihydrazone to the metal centre. The complexes show a single broad band in the region 665–690 nm with molar extinction coefficient in the region 110–125 dm³ cm⁻¹ mol⁻¹. The *d-d* bands in DMSO solution has slightly blue shifted as compared to that in solid state in **1** and **3**. This indicates interaction of DMSO molecule with metal centre in DMSO solution i.e. replacement of water molecule by DMSO molecules. However, the essential feature of the band in DMSO solution remains almost same as that in the solid state. This suggests that the stereochemistry of the complexes in solution as well as the solid state remains same i.e. distorted octahedral (Fig. 9).

Infrared spectra :

Some structurally significant IR bands for uncoordinated dihydrazone and complexes have been set out in Table 3. Although the ligand can exist in only one conformation in free state i.e. staggered the possibility of its existence is staggered, *syn-cis* and *anti-cis* configuration in the complexes cannot be ruled out^{16,37}. The heterotrinnuclear Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes **1-3** under study show characteristics peaks due to the ligation of the ligands to the metal centre in the KBr-phase IR spectra. The present ligands show strong broad bands in the region 3190–3235 cm⁻¹ and 3421–3446 cm⁻¹ which are attributed to arise due to stretching vibration of secondary -NH groups and naphtholic/phenolic -OH groups, respectively³⁸. All of the complexes show a strong broad band in the region 3421–3422 cm⁻¹. The essential feature of this band suggests that it arises due to ν_{OH} band of either lattice or coordinated water molecules. The complexes do not show the band in the region 3190–3235 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{NH} in free ligands. The absence of this band in the IR spectra of the complexes suggests that the ligand is present in enol form in all of the complexes³⁹. Another important and most characteristic feature of the IR spectra of the complexes is the absence of the band in the region 1659–1679 cm⁻¹ due to >C=O group in the uncoordinated dihydrazone. This corroborates the fact that the ligand is present in enol form in the complexes. The present ligands show a very sharp band in the region 1604–1623 cm⁻¹ which is assigned to stretching vibration of >C=N group. This band shifts to lower frequency by 7–21 cm⁻¹ sug-

Table 3. Structurally significant infrared (IR) bands (in cm⁻¹) for succinoyldihydrazones and their heterotrinnuclear zinc(II) and copper(II) complexes

Sl. No.	Ligand/complex	ν(OH+NH)	ν(C=O)	ν(C=N)	Amide II + ν(NCO ⁻)	ν(C-O)	ν(N-N)	ν(M-O) (phenolic)	ν(M-O) (enolate)	ν(M-N)	ν(NO ₃) ₂
					(C-O) Phenyl/Naphthyl						
	(H ₄ L ¹)	3421 (s) 3199 (s)	1659 (s)	1609 (s) 1622 (s)	1566 (s)	1269 (s)	1033 (s)	-	-	-	-
	(H ₄ L ²)	3446 (s) 3235 (s)	1675 (s)	1604 (sh) 1623 (s)	1530 (s)	1240 (s)	1031 (m)	-	-	-	-
	(H ₄ L ³)	3433 (m) 3190 (m)	1669 (s)	1615 (s)	1564 (s)	1267 (s)	1077 (m)	-	-	-	-
1.	[ZnCu ₂ (L ¹)(NO ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₈].2H ₂ O	3421 (s)	-	1601 (m)	1575 (s)	1477 (s)	1049 (m)	555 (w)	471 (w)	343 (w)	1383
2.	[ZnCu ₂ (L ²)(NO ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₈].2H ₂ O	3422 (s)	-	1615 (w)	1575 (s)	1470 (sh)	1041 (m)	520 (w)	474 (w)	355 (w)	850
3.	[ZnCu ₂ (L ³)(NO ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₈].2H ₂ O	3421 (s)	-	1598 (s)	1527 (s)	1473 (s)	1084 (m)	550 (w)	471 (w)	330 (w)	1384
								884 (w)			830
								385 (w)			1380
								385 (w)			833

gesting that $>C=N$ group is involved in bonding to the metal centre. Another important feature of the IR spectra of the complexes is that they show a new weak to strong band in the region $1473\text{--}1477\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This band is characteristic of the presence of NCO^- group⁴⁰. The essential features associated with this band in the IR spectra of the complexes suggest that the dihydrazone undergoes enolization. The complexes show a band in the region $1257\text{--}1299\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which corresponds to the strong band in the region $1240\text{--}1269\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the free dihydrazone ligand due to $\nu(C-O)$ (phenolic/naphtholic). The shift of this band to higher frequency by $10\text{--}49\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates bonding of phenolic/naphtholic oxygen atom to the metal centre via deprotonation⁴¹. The complexes show new bands in the region $500\text{--}555\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are assigned to $\nu(M-O)$ (phenolate/naphtholate)³⁵. The complexes show weak to medium intensity new bands in the region $864\text{--}887$ and 385 cm^{-1} , respectively. These bands are not visible in the spectrum of the free ligands. Hence, they are assigned to arise due to bridging metal atoms through oxygen atoms⁴². The position of the bands in the complexes is consistent with the involvement of enolate oxygen atoms in the bridge formation. The position of the bands suggests that they originate from the formation of mono-

bridge $(M \begin{array}{c} \diagup O \diagdown \\ \quad \quad \quad \end{array} M)$ ⁴³. The bands in the region $887\text{--}864\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to the antisymmetric vibrations while that around 385 cm^{-1} due to symmetric vibration of mono-

bridge $(M \begin{array}{c} \diagup O \diagdown \\ \quad \quad \quad \end{array} M)$, respectively⁴³.

The coordination of the nitrato group in these complexes is evident from the fact that the ν_3 band of ionic nitrate at 1360 cm^{-1} splits into ν_1 and ν_4 vibrations. The ν_1 band appears as a very strong band in the region $1380\text{--}1384\text{ cm}^{-1}$ while ν_4 band appears as a weak band in the region $830\text{--}850\text{ cm}^{-1}$. A very strong band around 1384 cm^{-1} in nitrate complexes is attributed to arise due to stretching vibration of NO_3^- group. The position of these bands is consistent with the presence of monodentately coordinated nitrato groups⁴⁴. Further, the complexes show a new band in the region $257\text{--}293\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This band is not visible in the low-frequency IR of ligands. Hence, it is attributed to have its origin due to M-O stretching vibration of coordinated nitrato group. The appearance of only

one band in this region further suggests that the nitrato group is unidentately coordinated to the metal centres^{45,46}.

Cyclic voltammetry :

The cyclic voltammetric data for the free ligand and the complexes have been given in Table 4 and the cyclic voltammogram for the complexes have been shown in Figs. 6–8. The uncoordinated ligands show one reductive and one oxidative wave in the region $+2.4$ to -2.4 V , respectively (Table 4). Ecluding the waves due to ligand centred electron transfer reactions, the metal-centred electron transfer waves have been identified and assigned. The complexes invariably show three reductive waves in the forward reductive scan at a scan rate of 100 mV/s . However, in the return oxidative scan, the complexes **1**, **2** and **3** show three, five and two oxidative waves, respectively. The reductive waves centred in the region -0.67 to -0.96 V and -1.23 to -1.55 V do not have their counterparts in the oxidative scan. Hence, the species

Table 4. Electrochemical data for the heterotrinnuclear zinc and copper complexes and its ligands at a scan rate of 100 mV/s

Sl. No.	Complex	E_{pc} (V)	E_{pa} (V)	ΔE (mV)
1.	[ZnCu ₂ (L ¹)(NO ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₈].2H ₂ O	-	+0.66	170
		-	+0.15	
		-0.19	-0.02	
		-0.86	-	
		-1.23	-	
		[-0.58] ^a	[-0.52] ^a	
2.	[ZnCu ₂ (L ²)(NO ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₈].2H ₂ O	-	+0.93	140
		-	+0.62	
		-	-0.24	
		-	-0.05	
		0.18	-0.04	
		-0.67	-	
3.	[ZnCu ₂ (L ³)(NO ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₈].2H ₂ O	-	+1.05	560
		-0.24	+0.32	
		-0.96	-	
		-1.55	-	
		[-0.88] ^a	[+0.47] ^a	

^aWaves due to uncoordinated ligands.

Fig. 6. Cyclic voltammetry of complex $[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^1)(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**) at 100 mV/s.

Fig. 7. Cyclic voltammetry of complex $[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^2)(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**2**) at 100 mV/s.

produced corresponding to these reductive waves are unstable and do not survive long in DMSO solution and return to the original species. These waves may be attributed to ligand centred reduction reactions. Further, the complexes show two new oxidative waves in the region +0.56 to +0.66 V and +0.93 to +1.05 V, respectively. The oxidative wave in the region +0.93 to +1.05 V is attributed to oxidation of first $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ group while that

in the region +0.56 to +0.66 V to second $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ group of coordinated ligand⁴⁷.

The complex **1** shows reductive wave at -0.19 V in the forward scan while the corresponding oxidative wave in the return anodic scan is observed at -0.02 V. The corresponding reductive and oxidative waves in complex **2** appear at -0.18 and -0.04 V, respectively. The separation between these waves in the complexes **1** and **2** are

Fig. 8. Cyclic voltammetry of complex $[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L}^3)(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**3**) at 100 mV/s.

170 and 140 mV, respectively. It may be noted that the separation of the peaks is more than 100 mV which is higher than that for an uncomplicated one electron redox process (0.06 V). Hence, the metal centred electron transfer reaction may be suggested to be quasi-reversible. Further, the complex **1** shows another oxidative wave at +0.15 V while the complex **2** shows two more oxidative waves at +0.05 and +0.24 V, respectively. These waves may also be attributed to metal centred electron transfer reactions. The oxidative waves at +0.15 and +0.05 in the complexes **1** and **2** may be attributed to $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}$ redox couple, while that at +0.24 in complex **2** to $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}$ redox couple. These oxidative waves do not have their counterpart in the reductive scan. This suggests that the metal centred species is unstable in DMSO solution and reverts back to the original species. The electron transfer reactions corre-

sponding to these redox waves may be shown below.

Complex **3** shows quite different cyclic voltammogram as compared to the complexes **1** and **2**. Complex **3** it shows peaks corresponding to electron transfer reactions centred on ligand at -0.96 and -1.55 V (reduction) and +1.05 V (oxidation), respectively. Apart from the ligand centred electron transfer reactions, the complex **3**, shows, another reductive wave at -0.24 V and corresponding oxidative wave at +0.32 V, respectively. The difference between these reductive and oxidative waves is 560 mV. This suggests that the metal centred electron transfer reaction is irreversible. In order to investigate whether the metal centred electron transfer reaction is irreversible or not, the cyclic voltammogram of the complex was recorded at scan rates of 50 and 30 mV. The difference between reductive and oxidative waves came out to be 432 and 244 mV, respectively. These observations support the fact that the metal centred electron transfer reaction in the complex is irreversible. In order to investigate whether the electron transfer reaction in the complexes **1** and **2** are quasi-reversible or reversible and the large separation between reductive and oxidative waves is due

Fig. 9. Suggested structure for copper(II)-zinc(II) complexes $[\text{ZnCu}_2(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{H}_4\text{L}=\text{H}_4\text{L}^1, \text{H}_4\text{L}^2, \text{H}_4\text{L}^3$).

to slow heterogeneous electron exchange only, the cyclic voltammogram of the complexes were recorded at slower scan rates of 70 and 50 mV/s also. The point of crucial importance is that when the scan rate is decreased from 100 to 70 to 50 mV/s, the position of the waves corresponding to metal centred electron transfer reaction change and the separation between them decreases from 170 to 160 to 60 mV for complex **1** and from 140 to 83 to 73 mV for the complex **2**, respectively. Such a voltammetric behaviour of the complexes shows that this is a quasi-reversible electron transfer process. However, this electron transfer process becomes almost completely reversible at a scan rate of 50 mV/s.

Experimental

Materials and measurements :

The metal salts, diethyl succinate, hydrazine hydrate, substituted salicylaldehydes and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde were E. Merck, Qualigens, Hi-Media or equivalent grade reagents and all manipulations were performed under aerobic conditions. The precursor monometallic zinc complexes $[\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{L}^n)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ ($\text{H}_4\text{L}^n = \text{H}_4\text{L}^1 - \text{H}_4\text{L}^3$) were prepared by literature method¹⁹. Copper and zinc were determined by standard literature procedure²³.

Instrumentation :

NMR spectra of the ligands were recorded on a FT-NMR (Bruker Avance II, 400 spectrometer) (^1H at 400 MHz and ^{13}C at 100 MHz) at 25 °C in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ solution using TMS as an internal standard. The mass losses were determined by heating the complexes at 110 and 180 °C in an electronic oven for 4 h at each temperature. The APCI mass spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Water ZQ 4000 Micromass spectrometer in DMSO solution. Molecular weight of the complexes was determined by freezing point depression method in DMSO ($K_f = 4.07$)²³ as a solvent, lowering of the freezing points of DMSO (18.5 °C) containing different amounts of complexes were made with a Beckman's freezing point depression instruments. C, H, N were determined by micro analytical methods. All conductance measurements were made at 1 KHz using Wayne Kerr B905 Automatic Precision Bridge. A dip-type conductivity cell having a platinised platinum electrode. The cell constant was determined using a standard KCl solution. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on

a Sherwood Magnetic Susceptibility Balance MSB-Auto. Diamagnetic corrections were carried out using Pascals constant²⁴. Electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in solid state and DMSO solution at $\sim 10^{-3}$ M concentration on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda-25 spectrophotometer. Electron paramagnetic resonance spectra of the complexes were recorded at X-band frequency on a Varian E-112 E-Line Century Service EPR spectrometer using TCNE ($g = 2.0027$) as an internal field marker. Variable temperature experiments were carried out with a Varian Variable Temperature accessory. Infrared spectra were recorded on a BX-III/FT-IR Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer in the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} in KBr discs. Far-IR spectra were recorded in the range 600–50 cm^{-1} . The electron transfer properties of the complexes were studied by cyclic voltammetry. The electrolytic cell comprises of three electrodes, the working electrode was Pt disk while the reference electrode and auxiliary electrode were Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) separated from the sample solution by a salt bridge. 0.1 mol L^{-1} TBAP was used as the supporting electrolyte.

Synthesis of compounds :

The precursor monometallic zinc complexes $[\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{L}^n)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ ($\text{H}_4\text{L}^n = \text{H}_4\text{L}^1 - \text{H}_4\text{L}^3$) were prepared by literature method¹⁹.

Synthesis of ligands :

Succinoyldihydrazine was prepared by reacting diethyl succinate (10.0 g, 49.50 mmol) with hydrazine hydrate (5.50 g, 110.00 mmol) under reflux for 4 h and recrystallized from methanol. Dihydrazones were prepared by reacting a solution of succinoyldihydrazine (10.37 mmol) in methanol with aldehydes and ketones (25.93 mmol) in hot methanol and refluxing the reaction mixture for 30 min. The precipitate obtained on cooling the solution was thoroughly washed with methanol and air dried to give H_4L^1 , H_4L^2 and H_4L^3 , respectively.

H_4L^1 : Colour : white; yield : 89%; m.p. 250 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ (354 g mol^{-1}) : C, 61.02; H, 5.08; N, 15.82. Found : C, 61.23; H, 5.06; N, 15.69; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) (δ ppm) : 11.30 (2H, s, OH), 10.2 (2H, s, NH), 8.27 (2H, s, CH=N), 6.9–7.6 (8H, m, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) (δ ppm) : 26.5, 27.2, 116.1, 116.3, 119.2, 119.4, 126.7, 129.4, 130.8, 130.9, 140.8, 140.9, 146.2, 146.3, 156.3, 157.3,

167.2, 167.6.

H_4L^2 : Colour : dark yellow; yield : 86%; m.p. 245 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{26}H_{22}N_4O_4$ (454 g mol⁻¹) : C, 68.72; H, 4.83; N, 12.33. Found : C, 68.99; H, 4.83; N, 12.65; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) (δ ppm) : 11.62 (2H, d, OH), 10.05 (2H, d, NH), 8.98 (2H, s, CH=N), 7.18–8.44 (8H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) (δ ppm) : 27.5, 28.7, 108.3, 112.2, 118.3, 118.6, 118.7, 120.4, 121.9, 122.0, 123.3, 124.1, 127.5, 127.7, 128.7, 128.8, 129.1, 131.5, 131.7, 132.3, 133.4, 138.3, 144.8, 157.7, 163.9, 167.3

H_4L^3 : Colour : light yellow; yield : 87%; m.p. 257 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{16}N_4O_4Br_2$ (512 g mol⁻¹) : C, 42.19; H, 3.13; N, 10.94. Found : C, 42.59; H, 3.11; N, 11.24; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) (δ ppm) : 11.36 (2H, d, OH), 10.2 (2H, s, NH), 8.2 (2H, s, CH=N), 6.9–7.6 (8H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) (δ ppm) : 26.4, 27.1, 110.3, 110.7, 118.3, 118.5, 130.4, 130.5, 133.1, 133.3, 138.3, 138.4, 143.7, 143.8, 155.4, 156.2, 167.8, 168.1.

Synthesis of [ZnCu₂(L¹)(NO₃)₂(H₂O)₈].2H₂O (1) :

[Zn(H₂L¹)(H₂O)₂] (2.0 g; 4.43 mmol) was suspended in acetonitrile (30 mL) and stirred vigorously to get a homogeneous suspension. This suspension was added into copper nitrate trihydrate solution maintaining [Zn(H₂L¹)(H₂O)₂] : Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O molar ratio 1 : 3 and was refluxed for 3 h which precipitated a green coloured compound. The compound was suction filtered in hot condition and washed three times with acetonitrile (30 mL each time) followed by ether and finally dried over anhydrous CaCl₂. Yield 2.60 g (78%), m.p. > 300 °C Anal : Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{34}N_6O_{20}Cu_2Zn$ (%) : Cu, 15.01; Zn, 7.72; C, 25.52; H, 3.54; N, 9.92. Found : Cu, 15.42; Zn, 7.89; C, 25.95; H, 3.50; N, 10.21; Mol. wt. (theo. : (846.49), exp. : (1020 ± 50)). Molar conductance (DMSO, Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) : 1.7.

Synthesis of [ZnCu₂(L²)(NO₃)₂(H₂O)₈].2H₂O (2) :

Complex (2) was also synthesized in the same way by following the above procedure using [Zn(H₂L²)(H₂O)₂] (2.0 g; 3.63 mmol) instead of [Zn(H₂L¹)(H₂O)₂]. Yield 2.23 g (72%), m.p. > 300 °C; Anal : Calcd. for $C_{26}H_{38}N_6O_{20}Cu_2Zn$ (%) : Cu, 13.43; Zn, 6.19; C, 32.96; H, 3.59; N, 8.87. Found : Cu, 13.13; Zn, 6.27; C, 33.41; H, 3.98; N, 7.03; Mol. wt. (theo. : (946.49), exp. :

(1180 ± 55)). Molar conductance (DMSO, Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) : 1.5.

Synthesis of [ZnCu₂(L³)(NO₃)₂(H₂O)₈].2H₂O (3) :

Complexes (3) was also prepared in the same way by following the above procedure using [Zn(H₂L³)(H₂O)₂] (2.0 g; 3.28 mmol) instead of [Zn(H₂L¹)(H₂O)₂]. Yield 2.45 g (85%), m.p. > 300 °C; Anal : Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{32}N_6O_{20}Br_2Cu_2Zn$ (%) : Cu, 12.65; Zn, 6.51; C, 21.50; H, 2.79; N, 8.36. Found : Cu, 13.02; Zn, 6.42; C, 21.83; H, 2.76; N, 8.23. Mol. wt. (theo. : (1004.49), exp. : (1230 ± 60)). Molar conductance (DMSO, Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) : 1.2.

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